

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Dear Reviewers,

We thank all the reviewers for their insightful and valuable comments. Hereinafter, revisions concerned by the Committee Comments and four reviewers are discussed below. Hope that we could make ourselves understood better and the confusions resolved.

1. Other Factors

Fig. 20. Performance of IOTPIM with and without considering compute time

Compute Times: We evaluate the impact arising from compute times for data-intensive workloads we used in the paper. In the evaluation, the CPU frequency is 2.5 GHZ, and the frequency of the PIM cores is the same as DRAM by 1200MHZ. Clearly, the compute time of the CPU and PIM logic are not the same.

Figure 20 shows the results without and with considering compute time (IOTPIM-w-CT). We see that IOTPIM and IOTPIM-w-CT yield the same performance. This is because the performance bottleneck for data-intensive applications lies in memory accesses, and the memory efficiency of CPU and PIM logic has a significant gap.

Fig. 21. Performance of IOTPIM with and without considering the usage of core or shared resources

Resource Usage: To analyze the impact of the overall system usage of cores and other shared resources, Figure 21 shows the performance of IOTPIM with or without considering the overall system usage of cores (IOTPIM-w-UC) and the shared resources (IOTPIM-w-SR).

IOTPIM-w-UC prioritizes offloading PIM instructions of busy cores, while idle cores will execute PIM instructions by themselves. For IOTPIM-w-SR, we consider only the on-chip LLC shared resources. If the LLC resource is not fully occupied, PIM instructions will keep the core side without offloading for fully exploiting the LLC capability.

Compared to IOTPIM, IOTPIM-w-UC and IOTPIM-w-SR degrade performance by 13.13%, 5.77%. Since the PIM instruction efficiency is dominated by memory accesses, directly offloading these PIM instructions to the PIM side will not occupy shared resources in the CPU side. This allows releasing more shared resources to boost overall system efficiency.

Fig. 22. The offloading accuracy of different cache hierarchy with different cache size

2. Generality

To analyze the generality of IOTPIM, we consider different system configurations below.

Cache Configuration: Figure 22 shows the offloading accuracy of IOTPIM on the following three types of modern cache hierarchies with different cache hierarchies and sizes.

- Intel-Kentsfield XE¹ with a two-level cache hierarchy of 64KB L1 cache and 8MB L2 cache.
- AMD Zen 2 microarchitecture² with a three-level cache hierarchy of 32KB cache, 512KB cache, and 16MB L3 cache.
- Intel Broadwell microarchitecture³ with a four-level cache hierarchy of 64KB L1 cache, 256KB L2 cache, 6MB L3 cache, and 128MB L4 cache.

Under various cache configurations, IOTPIM still preserves the high accuracy for the two-, three-, and four-level cache hierarchies by 90.91%, 92.27%, and 91.03%, respectively. Note that the cache size is different in different cache hierarchies. This also demonstrates that IOTPIM is applicable for different cache hierarchies and sizes.

Fig. 23. The offloading accuracy of the three level cache hierarchy using different latencies

Different Cache Latencies: We also analyze the three-level cache hierarchy with different latencies. Figure 23 shows the offloading accuracy with different L1-L2-L3 cache latencies.

(1) **Type 1:** 4 cycle, 7 cycle, 27 cycle, (2) **Type 2:** 6 cycle, 12 cycle, and 31 cycle, and (3) **Type 3:** 10 cycle, 18 cycle, 40 cycle. With different cache latencies, IOTPIM still has high offload accuracy by 91.98%, 91.16%, and 91.54%, respectively.

Fig. 24. The offloading accuracy of different PIM architectures

Different PIM Architectures: We also implement IOTPIM on the emerging 3D stacked PIM architecture. Figure 24

¹<https://ark.intel.com/content/www/us/en/ark/products/codename/23489/products-formerly-kentsfield.html>

²<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zen2>

³[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Broadwell_\(microarchitecture\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Broadwell_(microarchitecture))

shows the offloading accuracy of IPTPIM on the DIMM-level PIM architecture and the 3D stacked PIM architecture. We see that IOTPIM achieves almost the same offloading accuracy by 91.89%, and 91.41%, respectively, demonstrating the generality of IOTPIM for different general-purpose PIM architectures.

3. Fair Comparison

Fig. 25. Performance of IOTPIM against the baseline and four state-of-the-art PIM offloading techniques

Fig. 26. Energy consumptions of IOTPIM against the baseline and four state-of-the-art PIM offloading techniques

Figure 25 and Figure 26 evaluate the performance and energy consumption of IOTPIM against TDO-CIM and PRIMO on the specialized PIM architectures in their papers, respectively. Compared to TDO-CIM, IOTPIM offers $1.34\times$ speedup and $1.22\times$ energy reduction, on average. In addition, IOTPIM also outperforms PRIMO by $1.28\times$ speedup and $1.42\times$ energy reduction, on average.

4. Instruction Offloading

Fig. 27. The number of offloading instructions of four state-of-the-art PIM offloading techniques

Figure 27 shows the offloading instruction breakdown of different PIM offloading techniques. Consider different applications have significantly different amounts of offloading instructions.

We select a representative execution snapshot for each application for better scale sensing. Figure 27 shows the results. We see that offloading performance of GraphPIM, TDO-CIM, and PRIMO are rather limited due to their specific offloading operations. LLCMIRO considers only the LLC locality and thus leads to wrong instruction offloading for many applications (e.g., machine learning applications). In contrast, IOTPIM improves accuracy significantly by considering the overall cache hierarchy for instruction offloading.

Fig. 28. Pre-run analysis time normalized to the execution time

Fig. 29. Performance comparison between the baseline and IOTPIM with or without per-input analysis for GIN

5. Motivation

The cache model looks simple but effective in yielding a fast yet accurate solution. In addition, building such a model is challenging and also obtaining the parameters for the model is complex.

First, the instruction offloading decision must be determined at the compile time to generate the instruction binary for a fixed compute logic. We have to use the instruction offloading model to determine whether the offloading can improve performance. However, the parameters (i.e., the number of hits in each memory level) of the offloading model are unknown before the actual execution.

Second, the application pre-run can be used to collect the parameters required by the offloading model, but it may introduce prohibitive overheads. Figure 28 shows the pre-run analysis time overhead over the normal execution time. The pre-run analysis overhead can be $11.62\times$ the execution time, since a huge amount of hits in each memory level for the instructions needs to be recorded.

Third, different datasets may have different cache locality (even for the same instruction). The instruction offloading decision can be inaccurate, if the parameters are considered from a limited set of input datasets. Figure 29 depicts the performance results for the *Graph Isomorphism Networks* (GIN) application in two ways of: (1) *the one-time pre-run analysis on Arxiv dataset* and (2) *the pre-run analyses for each input*. We see that the offloading decision from some datasets can cause performance degradation for other input datasets. For instance, *Cora* has 41.22% performance loss. In contrast, the per-input pre-run analysis improves the performance of the application with the accurate decision, but expensive pre-run analysis overhead incurs.

To avoid the expensive overhead of the per-input pre-run analysis, a prediction model can be useful. We would like to predict the offloading decision accurately as if the per-input pre-run analysis were performed.